

Women in the Irish War Hospital Supply Organisation

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The Letters 1916-1923 team collect and publish Irish-themed letters, but we are also actively analysing the life stories of the people whose correspondence we add to our database. At the moment, we are trying to find out more about the volunteers who were involved in the **Irish War Hospital Supply Organisation** (till spring 1919), helping to produce and ship surgical supplies for military hospitals in the British Empire, Belgium or France. In the current issue of [History Ireland \(Nov/Dec\)](#), we give a first impression of our current research, and there is more to explore.

In the context of Irish contributions to the First World War, the Irish War Hospital Supply Organisation (IWSO) is particularly noteworthy because it was essentially staffed and run by women. This predominantly female war effort was very visible and well respected at the time. However, these women were often marginalised in later historiography. Re-discovering the personal or professional connections between female volunteers and their relationships with government bodies, the armed forces or the Red Cross offers a fascinating insight into early-twentieth-century social hierarchies, gender roles, and how the experience of the Great War altered them.

The war called for the active commitment of every member of society and gave women an opportunity to carry out work which had previously been male-dominated or entirely restricted to men. Newspapers and specialist journals such as *The Hospital* praised the “noble women workers in the war” (*The Hospital*, Volume 62, 21 April 1917). The report [“Women of the War”](#), first published in 1917, painted a colourful and differentiated picture of female wartime labour as it highlighted the achievements of women in fields as diverse as nursing, science and car repairing.

40 Merrion Square, Dublin, location of the former Irish War Hospital Supply Depot

Although wartime charities were frequently presided over by aristocratic patrons, many women who occupied influential managerial and secretarial positions were in fact members of well-to-do Protestant and Catholic middle-class families whose education and social skills were highly valued. In the Irish War

Hospital Supply Depot in 40 Merrion Square, which was the main depot for medical supplies in Ireland, **Letitia Overend**, the daughter of an affluent Protestant solicitor, and **Eleanor Dallas Pratt (née Palles)**, the Catholic wife of a respected Dublin surgeon, served as Honorary Secretaries. In this capacity, Eleanor Dallas Pratt and Letitia Overend took care of official correspondence with tool dealers, government officials and different customers across

the British Isles. The [Manchester Central Library](#), for instance, have kindly permitted us to digitise letters from a three-sided correspondence between the Irish War Hospital Supply Depot, the Belgian Funds Committee in Manchester, and the Belgian Red Cross in London. The Belgian Funds Committee, represented by John H. Billinge as Hon. Secretary and Treasurer, arranged for the Irish War Hospital Supply Depot, represented by Eleanor Dallas Pratt, to regularly ship medical items to the Belgian Red Cross in London, where they were used to treat wounded Belgian soldiers. The bound volume of Belgian Red Cross letters kept in Manchester also contains detailed lists of all dispatched supplies alongside letters of thanks or supplication from soldiers and their families. The letters on behalf of the Belgian Red Cross were written by M. Albert Maeterlinck and C. E. R. Abbott. Maeterlinck was a Belgian national and returned home in January 1919. We are looking forward to making this correspondence public soon.

Draft family tree of the Palles family, the birth family of Eleanor (Bruce) Dallas Pratt, who served as Hon. Secretary to the Irish War Hospital Supply Depot in Dublin.

Besides, we have been able to draft a family tree of Eleanor (Bruce) Dallas Pratt's birth family on the basis of the Irish census and testamentary records, but we need your support in completing it. Eleanor's son, [Captain Mervyn Palles Pratt](#), died in his twenties, and we do not know if her daughter ever married. Descendants of Andrew Christopher Palles are now living in Australia, but we would also like to learn about family members in Ireland. If you know more about Eleanor Dallas Pratt or other women who volunteered in the Irish War Hospital Supply Depot in Dublin or local workrooms, please [get in touch](#). We will be glad to feature your stories on our website. Your contribution could help us uncover some of the hidden lives

of Irish women a century ago and give us a better understanding of volunteering and charitable work during the First World War.

"Service – surgical dressings for war relief", lithograph, photographed by and retrieved from the Library of Congress, www.loc.gov/item/2002722579.

The biographies of women who worked in the Irish War Hospital Supply Organisation are a major research interest of the Letters 1916-1923 team, and we need your help in uncovering these forgotten stories. Last week, we asked for your help in finding out more about [Eleanor \(Bruce\) Dallas Pratt](#), who served as Honorary Secretary in the Irish War Hospital Supply Depot in Dublin. According to the final report published in 1919, this depot had more than eighty sub-depots across the country, and women played a vital role in their day-to-day management. Local work parties produced all kinds of medical and surgical supplies from papier-maché artificial limbs to bandages, but [sphagnum moss wound dressings](#) were perhaps the most important item shipped from Ireland. Sphagnum moss was sourced in several parts of the British Empire, including

Scotland and Canada, because it served as a cheap and widely available replacement for cotton cloth, which ran short during the First World War. Moss collection for medical purposes was introduced to Ireland in autumn 1915 and soon professionalised. Many volunteers (above all women and children) contributed to the time-consuming work.

Locating places of medical supply production in Ireland

Contemporary maps and the [various reports published by the War Hospital Supply Organisation](#) in Dublin give us an impression how wide-spread and well-organised the production of all medical supplies was. [University College Dublin](#) have published an early twentieth-century [map of Irish sphagnum moss depots on their website](#). Other work parties and regional depots are mentioned in reports held by the [National Library of Ireland](#) and in a [list of British war hospital supply depots](#) assembled by **Sue Light**. Based on these data, we have created a [zoomable map of Ireland](#) which highlights general war hospital supply depots (green), sphagnum moss depots (blue) and local work parties (marked in red, activities not always specified).

War hospital supply depots and sphagnum moss collection centres in Ireland (1916-1919).

These centres were active at different times between 1916 and 1919, and we appreciate your support in researching their development. Tracing depots and work parties can be challenging because estate and town names may have changed, or because Irish place names were spelled inconsistently in the sources. The 325 nodes we have identified so far were mainly situated on the Irish coast or on major transportation routes (e.g. the Royal Canal and railway lines). Dublin and Belfast were the most important harbours for the shipping of all war hospital supplies to the British army and allied organisations such as the Anglo-Belgian Committee of the Belgian Red Cross. At least sixteen places (marked in yellow) functioned both as sphagnum moss and general supply depots.

In recent years, **Dr. Clara Cullen** (UCD Library) has already conducted [extensive research in the overall organisation of sphagnum moss collection and processing in Ireland](#), but little is known about individual volunteers. Therefore, we need to rely on hints in private letters to reconstruct the social networks and motivations of women who dedicated their time and energy to this demanding work on the home front.

Lady Clonbrock, courtesy of the National Library of Ireland, Dublin

Lady Clonbrock and the sphagnum moss collection in County Galway

One collection of letters in the the Letters 1916-1923 database that contains such hints is the correspondence of [Augusta Caroline Dillon, Lady Clonbrock](#). This correspondence includes [three letters](#) relating to the efforts of **Lady Clonbrock and her female acquaintances** to establish a sphagnum moss sub-depot in County Galway. The original letters are now in the possession of the [National Library of Ireland](#) but have been photographed and transcribed for our project. If you know more about women who worked as moss collectors or elsewhere in the Irish war hospital supply system, please share your stories with us. With your help, we are hoping to bring some of the uncredited achievements of Irish women to the attention of the public.

Further reading:

Cullen, Clara. 'War Work on the Home Front: The Central Sphagnum Depot for Ireland at the Royal College of Science for Ireland, 1915-1919'. In *Medicine, Health and Irish Experiences of Conflict, 1914-45*, edited by David Durnin and Ian Miller, 155–70. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2017.

Irish War Hospital Supply Organisation. *Third Annual Report of the Sphagnum Department of the Irish War Hospital Supply Organisation*. Dublin: Thom, 1919.

Reilly, Eileen. 'Women and Voluntary War Work'. In *Ireland and the Great War: 'A War to Unite Us All'?*, edited by Adrian Gregory and Senia Paseta, 49–72. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2002.

Burke, Tim. "The Other Women of 1916." *20th Century Social Perspectives*, 20th-century / Contemporary History, 14, no. 5 (Sep/Oct) (2006). <https://www.historyireland.com/20th-century-contemporary-history/the-other-women-of-1916/>.

Department of the Director-General of Voluntary Organisations. *National Scheme of Co-Ordination of Voluntary Effort Resulting from the Formation of the D.G.V.O. Department, Appendices 3 and 4 : Being a Detailed Record of the Work of the Recognised Associations*. London, 1920. <http://hdl.handle.net/2027/umn.31951002310080a>.

Hendley, Matthew C. "Peter Grant. Philanthropy and Voluntary Action in the First World War: Mobilizing Charity." *The American Historical Review* 120, no. 2 (April 1, 2015): 718–19. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/120.2.718>.

McLaren, Barbara. *Women of the War*. New York, [c. 1918]. <http://hdl.handle.net/2027/loc.ark:/13960/t3rv12j4c>.

Sanz, Catherine. "How the War Became Irish Women's Work | Ireland | The Times." The Times, March 21, 2018. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/how-women-became-nation-s-war-backbone-tcg9njh68?t=ie>.

Thom's Irish Who's Who :A Biographical Book of Reference of Prominent Men and Women in Irish Life at Home and Abroad. Dublin, 1923.
<http://hdl.handle.net/2027/bc.ark:/13960/t7dr37617>.